

ABU ALI IBN SINO ASARLARIDA AXLOQIY FAZILATLAR TAHLILI

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Annotasiya: Maqolada Abu Ali ibn Sino asarlaridagi axloqiy, ta'limiy masalalarni bugungi kundagi ahamiyatiga oid fikrlar nazariy jihatdan bayon etilgan. Yoshlarni ijtimoiy-axloqiy tarbiyalash, ularning ijtimoiy faolligini shakllantirish yoshlarga oid siyosatning muhim vazifalaridan biri etib belgilanganligi tahlil etilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Axloq, qadriyat, axloqiy tarbiyalash, ma'naviyat, ta'lim, tarbiya, ilm-fan.

ANALYSIS OF MORAL VIRTUES IN THE WORKS OF ABU ALI IBN SINA

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Annotation: The article theoretically describes the views on the importance of moral and educational issues in the works of Abu Ali Ibn Sina today. It is analyzed that socio-ethical education of young people, formation of their social activity is defined as one of the important tasks of youth policy.

Key words: Morality, value, moral education, spirituality, education, training, science.

АНАЛИЗ ПРАВСТВЕННЫХ ДОБРОДЕТЕЛЕЙ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ АБУ АЛИ ИБН СИНЫ

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Аннотация: В статье теоретически изложены взгляды на важность морально-воспитательных вопросов в творчестве Абу Али ибн Сины в наши дни. Анализируется, что социально-этическое воспитание молодежи, формирование ее социальной активности определяется как одна из важных задач молодежной политики.

Ключевые слова: Мораль, ценности, нравственное воспитание, духовность, воспитание, воспитание, наука.

At the present time, difficult, but energetic and consistent processes are taking place in Uzbekistan, such as the democratization of all spheres of social life, the realization of the political and national identity of citizens, the formation of new democratic values, the construction of an open democratic, legal state, and the formation of civil society institutions. Liberalization of society further expands the possibilities of strengthening social stability in our country. Democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the universal principles that a person, his freedom of life, honor and other indivisible rights are the highest value. Since the declaration of independence in Uzbekistan, the development of democratic principles, the rights of the nations living on the Uzbek soil, the development of the traditions and customs of each nation, and the further strengthening of respect for them have been carried out.

Social and moral education of young people, formation of their social activity was defined as one of the important tasks of youth policy. In accordance with this law, the determination of the principles on which the youth policy is based is a clear proof of this. Examples of them include "caring for young people regardless of their national, racial, language, religious affiliation, social status, gender, education and political views", "legal and social protection of young people", "supporting youth initiatives, guaranteeing the choice of the way to realize their interests by young people within the framework of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan", "the youth in the formation and implementation of programs and policies for the development of society, especially the life of the youth of the Republic direct participation", "the unity of rights and duties, freedom and civil responsibility". In today's dangerous times, it is important to the spiritual property of all mankind to ensure social stability, live in peace and work in harmony among nations. The role of the spiritual heritage of our great ancestors who contributed is incomparable. As President Sh.Mirziyoev noted: "It is known that thousands of scientists, scholars, great thinkers, poets, and saints have grown up from the land of our country, which is the crossroads of ancient cultures and civilizations, in the Middle Ages. Their invaluable heritage in the field of exact sciences and religious sciences is considered the spiritual property of all mankind.

In the philosophical views of the great speech artist Saadi Shirazy, ideas such as encouraging people and nations to live in peace and harmony are leading. Among his wisdom

All people are children of people,
One is good, one is busy with evil.
You can't find an ant from someone,
One is less honorable than a dog

lines are found. In fact, all people have the same appearance, but their actions are different. According to religious mythology, it is interpreted that all humans are actually the children of Adam and Eve. All people live under the great honorable name of mankind. But some live their lives with goodness and goodnes, and some with evil and enmity. Some people are so innocent that they don't even hurt an ant, and some people don't even have the honor of a dog. In Shirozi's opinion, the minds of people who fight even for issues that can be solved by peace, ending with compromise, are actually rusty. Saadi Shirozi says that whoever follows Satan's judgment, he will wander among his sins for the rest of his life. Also, beware of the stranger who appears in the shell of a friend, who can take you out of your religion and humanity. Look for ways to reconcile, compromise and be united on the battlefield, even with a sword in your hand. Be kind to one another and do not hurt each other, because grudges and quarreling with each other will cause disunity and disintegration. Shirozi states that the best virtue for people is harmony, peace and unity and writes:

When united, the ants become a union,
The skin of a lion is smooth.

In these lines, it is suggested that if people live harmoniously and harmoniously, no malicious ideas can influence them and lead them away from the right path.

In Uzbekistan, the development of our moral values is important in the process of building a society, the strategic goal of building a civil society. Achieving the harmony of the spirituality of a free person, modern democratic ideas and national-spiritual values is also supported by the literary-scientific heritage of Farobi, Yusuf Khas Hajib, Ibn Sina, Jami, Navoi about the virtuous society. It is one of the most important tasks to provide a better education to the mature generation of Uzbekistan and to introduce the ways of creativity of our great thinkers in the process of teaching them, and to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism for a more independent Uzbekistan.

One of our ancestors who made the name of Bukhara known to the whole world was Abu Ali al-Husayn ibn Abdullah ibn al-Hasan ibn Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), who was born in the ancient village of Afshana in Bukhara, known to the West as Avicenna. In the Eastern sources, the scientist is often honored with the title "Shaykh" or "Shaykh ar-Rais". This name, which means the leader of the sages, scholars, and expresses the love of the people, is a sign of the East's and West's respect for the scientist. The work that brought Ibn Sina world fame is "Al-Qanun fi-t-tib" consisting of five books. It is a work that has been raised to a high level. This work was abridged and translated from Arabic to Latin in the 12th century. Later, "Urjuza" about medicine was translated into French, English, German and Romanian in the 16th-17th centuries. , includes parts of logic, physics, mathematics and metaphysics.

The most important means of moral education is to have a one-on-one conversation without touching the child's ego and pride. Ibn Sina believes that the formation of moral characteristics in a child in unity with work, physical and mental education is the main factor in making him a human being.

Abu Ali ibn Sina believed that the first criterion for reaching maturity is to acquire knowledge, and he encouraged people to acquire knowledge. Noting the need to educate children at school, he emphasizes the need to adhere to the following principles in education:

- when teaching children, don't book them all at once;
- imparting knowledge by going from light to heavy in education;
- exercises should be suitable for children's age;
- pay attention to teaching at school as a team;
- taking into account the inclination, interest and ability of children in education;
- combining training with physical exercises.

Ibn Sina said that the social environment that surrounds him plays a special role in the formation of a person, that this environment not only affects a person's knowledge of the world around him, but also affects the formation of good or bad aspects in his character, therefore, he is careful in raising children. Ishaq, it radiates the need to keep him away from a bad social environment. Ibn Sina proves the important importance of physical education along with intellectual and moral education in human development both theoretically and practically. He emphasizes the need to take care of the child even before he is born, to start education from infancy.

In the educational views of Ibn Sina, the mental, moral, aesthetic and physical development of a person is interpreted as the main criterion for his maturity.

Today's pedagogue, based on his knowledge and skills, should have the ability to change the public opinion towards the priorities in the field of education today.

That is, to teach students to be able to operate independently, to use the flow of information wisely, in the era of increasing information and educational environment, high scientific and technical development, globalization, increasing environmental problems. The main task is to be aware of the science of logic and to increase philosophical thinking. For this, it is necessary to create the opportunity and conditions for continuous independent work for students. Based on this, the task of professors and teachers in the field of education is not only to impart knowledge, but also to prepare students for independent research, work and thinking, analysis, comparison, quick updating and replenishment of knowledge during life. The spiritual and educational thinking and the rich scientific and cultural legacy of the great scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sina serves as a basis for solving these urgent tasks for pedagogues and learners.

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